

IMPACT OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY ADVANCEMENT ON HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT: A STUDY WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO YENEPLOYA UNIVERSITY, DERALAKATTE IN MANGALORE

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Abstract:

This study was intended to evaluate the impact of information technology on Human Resource Management. The study was guided by three distinctive objectives related to the topic that is to know the demographic details of employees, to find out the impact of information technology on human resource management and to know the satisfaction level of employees towards the benefits of information technology on human resource management. The study employed descriptive research design. Primary and secondary data sources were used. The primary data was collected by using a structured questionnaire method and secondary data sources are internet, journals and newspaper. Fifty administrative employees of Yeneploya University, Deralakatte in Mangalore were taken as respondents.

Index Terms: Information Technology, Advancement, HRM & Satisfaction Level Etc

1. Introduction:

The advent of computer and internet made much impact on business world. The business functions cannot be performed without the use of computer technology. The impacts of computer technology were in all the areas of business organisation. The advancement of information technology resulted much impact on human resource practices and it play an important role in various aspects of human resource management i.e. recruitment, training, performance management, data storage and retrieval as well as information technology helped employees' work more simple and easy way and also reduced the work burden of people in the organisation. Employees are getting accurate and up to data information through internet and related software which reduced various employment and labour problems in the organisation.

Yeneploya University is a deemed university in Mangalore was established in 2009. There are 60 administrative workers are employed in different designation in Yeneploya university. There are 7 departments in administrative section i.e. HRD, Accounts, Academic, Examination, Manager Section, Admission and auditing. All the departments are using information technology in various ways. They have got different soft wares to do their work more accurately and to assess information easily when required. They have got separate salary and income tax software which automatically do all deductions and calculations. They have also separate software to pay the bills of customers. Employee promotion, service, leave, experience and increment calculation can be done automatically by the help of data stored in the computer and related software. The organization also has Biometric system to mark employees' attendance. Here employees in and exit time automatically recorded in punching machine when the employee put their thumb on punching machine. Biometric helps to access various details of employees regarding their casual leave, loss of pay and late comers' details.

Internal auditor also can perform his auditing work more efficiently through the help of information technology. The advancement on information technology made many impact on human resource management.

2. Objectives of the Study:

- The study focuses on the following objectives:
- ✓ To know the demographic details of the employees.
 - ✓ To find out the impact of information technology on human resource management.
 - ✓ To understand the satisfaction level of employees as regards the role and impact of Information technology on their work.

3. Methodology:

In research method constitutes the base and standard through which data is collected and analysed. It is an important aspect of research. The main purpose of this is to have a clear idea of research procedure that has been followed for the study. It contains a brief description about how the entire study has been carried out. It includes sample, research design, universe of the study, tools of data collection and data processing and analysis.

Sample: For the purpose of the study sample of 50 respondents will be considered. A simple random technique is used for collecting data.

Research Design: In view of the nature of the problem and to accomplish the objectives of the study, researcher decided to use descriptive research design

Universe of the Study: Universe of the study means geographical area selected for the study. The universe of the study comprises Employees of Yenepoya University, Deralakatte in Mangalore.

Tools of Data Collection: The questionnaire is used as a main instrument in collecting the information. The primary data is collected through questionnaire method and the secondary data was collected from published as well as unpublished sources such as books, journals, internet etc.

Data Processing and Analysis: The data collected was coded, tabulates, interpreted and analysed.

4. Analysis and Interpretation:

Profile of the Respondents:

Age (years)	No. of respondents	Percentage
20- 25	02	04
25- 30	08	16
30- 35	12	24
35- 40	16	32
Above 40	12	24
Total	50	100
Sex	No. of respondents	Percentage
Male	15	30
Female	35	70
Total	50	100
Marital Status	No. of respondents	Percentage
Single	18	36
Married	32	64
Total	50	100
Educational Qualification	No. of respondents	Percentage
SSLC	0	0
PUC	05	10
Graduates	37	74

Post Graduates	06	12
Other	02	04
Total	50	100
Designation	No. of respondents	Percentage
First Division Super Intendant	05	10
First division assistant	20	40
Second division assistant	15	30
Clerk	04	08
Typist	03	06
Computer assistant	02	04
Attender	01	02
Total	50	100

The table no. 4.0 showing that Majority (32%) of the respondents were come under the age group of 35 to 40 years, 24% of the respondents were come under the age group of above 40 years, 24% of the respondents were in between the age group of 30 to 35 years, 16% of the respondents were in between the age group of 25 to 30 years and 4% of the respondents were in between the age group of 20- 25 years. The age group of the respondents indicates that majority of the respondents have got more service in this organisation.

The majority (70%) of the respondents were female and 30% of the respondents were male. Compared to male employees majority of women employees are engaged in administration work of the organisation.

The majority (64%) of the respondents were married and 36% of the respondents were single.

The majority (74%) of the respondents were graduates, 12% of the respondents are post graduates, 10% of the respondents are PUC holders and 4% of the respondents come under other category. It says majority of the respondents are qualified and they are handling more responsible jobs in this organisation.

The majority (40%) of the respondents are working as First Division assistant, 30% of the respondents are working as Second Division Assistant, 10% of the respondents are working as First Division Super intendant, 8% of the respondents are working as Clerks, 6% of the respondents are working as Typists and 2% of the respondents are working as Attenders. It indicates that majority of the respondents are working in better position in the organisation.

5. Employees Satisfaction towards the Benefits of Information Technology:

Particular	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Very Satisfied	40	80
Somewhat satisfied	10	20
Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied	0	0
Somewhat dissatisfied	0	0
Very Dissatisfied	0	0
Total	50	100

The above table and figure showing that majority (80%) of the respondents are very satisfied with the benefits of information technology on human resource management and 20% of the respondents were somewhat satisfied towards the benefits of information technology on human resource management. It indicates that the majority of the respondents are satisfied with the current benefits of information technology because it provides accurate and reliable information about human resource of the organization.

5.2 Impact of Information Technology Has Reduced Work Burden of Employees:

Particular	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Strongly Disagree	0	0
Disagree	0	0
Unsure	0	0
Agree	32	64
Strongly Agree	18	36
Total	50	100

The above table and figure shows that the majority (64%) of the respondents said that they agree that information technology has reduced the work burden of employees and 36% of the respondents strongly agree with this statement. It shows that internet and related software helped the employees to reduce various works which they have done manually. It helped them to engage in other activities of the organisation.

5.3 Advancement of Information Technology Increased Work Efficiency and Made Work Simple and Easy:

Particular	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Strongly disagree	0	0
Disagree	0	0
Unsure	0	0
Strongly Agree	04	08
Agree	46	92
Total	50	100

The above table and figure shows that the majority (92%) of the respondents said that advancement of information technology helped them to increase their work efficiency and to make their work more simple and easy. 8% of the respondents were strongly agreed with the above statement. It means the information technology helped them provide accurate and reliable information. Easily accessible information helped the employees to perform their work more efficiently.

5.4. Impact of Information Technology on HRM:

Particular	Strongly Disagree		Disagree		Unsure		Agree		Strongly Agree	
	No. of respondents	Percentage								
Managerial Functions	0		0	0	0	0	22	44	28	56
Biometric	0		0	0	2	4	15	30	33	66
Assess and distribute information	0		0	0	0		0	0	50	100
Data storage and retrieval	0		0	0	0		0	0	50	100
Policy formulation	0	0	0	0	5	10	10	20	35	70
To make corrective actions	0	0	0	0	4	8	30	60	16	32
Legal decision	0	0	0	0	10	20	30	60	10	20

The above table indicates the respondents' different opinion towards the impact of advancement of information technology on human resource management. The majority (56%) of the respondents strongly agree that the advancement of information technology made impact on managerial functions of the organization and 44% of the respondents agree with this statement. All the respondents (100%) strongly agree that the information technology helped to easily access and distribute information on human resource management. The majority (66%) of the respondents strongly agree that the application of biometric help the management by providing accurate information regarding employees' leaves and absenteeism. And 33% of the respondents agree with the above statement and 2% of the respondent unsure about the above statement.

All the respondents' i.e.100% agree that the advancement of information technology helped for data storage and retrieval. The majority (70%) of the respondent

strongly agree that the advancement of information technology has made impact on policy formulation, 20 % of the respondents were agree with the above statement and 10% of the respondents were unsure about this. The majority 60%) of the respondents agree that the management has taken correct decisions with the help of accurate data available through related software and internet. 32% of the respondents strongly agree with the above statement and 8% of the respondents were unsure about the statement. The majority (60%) of the respondents agree that the management can easily take legal decision after the advancement of information technology, 20% of the respondents strongly agree with the above statement and 20% of the respondents were unsure about the statement.

5.5 Information Technology Enables Human Resource Department to Connect Through Internet with Other Department to Access Information of Human Resource Management:

Particular	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Strongly disagree	0	0
Disagree	0	0
Unsure	0	0
Strongly Agree	12	24
Agree	38	76
Total	50	100

The above table indicates that majority (76%) of the respondents were agree that advancement of information technology has enabled human resource department to connect with other department to access various information regarding employees, 24% of the respondents were strongly agree with this statement. Therefore the above data shows that all the respondents were aware about information technology benefited to human resource department to access information of employees working in other departments.

5.6 Employee Aware About Latest Trends in Policy Making, Activities and Employment Practices:

Particular	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Strongly disagree	0	0
Disagree	0	0
Unsure	15	30
Strongly Agree	10	20
Agree	25	50
Total	50	100

The above table and figure highlights that majority (50%) of the respondents agree that advancement of information technology helped them to aware of the latest trends in policy making, activities and employment practices. 30% of the respondents unsure about the above statement and 20% of the respondents were strongly agree that they aware about latest trends in policy making, activities, and employment practices through internet and data available in computer. t shows that management is creating a good rapport and commutation with their employees by providing information through internet regarding latest policies, various activities and employment practices related to work of the organisation. It helped the employees to understand their duties and responsibilities easily and to perform their work with expectation of management.

5.7 Information Technology Has Enabled the Management to Take Correct Decisions and Actions About Human Resources With the Help of Accurate Data And Up- To- Date Information Available in Internet and Related Software:

Particular	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Strongly disagree	0	0
Disagree	0	0
Unsure	06	12
Agree	29	58
Strongly Agree	15	30
Total	50	100

The majority (58%) of the respondents agree that management has taken correct actions and decisions about human resource management through accurate data and up- to- date information available from internet and related software. 30% of the respondents strongly agree with the above statement and 12% of the respondents were unsure about this statement. The above data indicates that majority of the respondents agree that the information technology helped the management to access various information of employees regarding their leave, compensation, promotion, service, discipline procedure etc. which enables them to make correct decisions relating to human resource matters.

5.8 Employee Suggestion to Improve the Role of Information Technology on Human Resource Management:

Suggestions	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	40	80
No	10	20
Total	50	100

The above table and figure show that majority (80%) of the respondents said that they need more latest technologies which help them to perform their work more easily i.e. software related to induction programme, training, refresher courses with the help of information technology. 20% of the respondents don't have any suggestions towards the benefits of information technology.

6. Findings:

Based on the analysis and interpretation of data, the following findings can be made:

- ✓ Majority (80%) of the respondents are very satisfied with the benefits of information technology on human resource management due to accurate data available through internet and related software.
 Majority (64%) of the respondents said that they strongly agree that information technology has reduced the work burden of employees. It shows that internet and related software helped the employees to reduce manual works. It helped them to involve in other responsibilities of the organisation.
- ✓ Majority (92%) of the respondents said that advancement of information technology helped them to increase their work efficiency and to make their work more simple and easy. It means the information technology helped them provide accurate and reliable information whenever required.
- ✓ The majority (56%) of the respondents strongly agree that the advancement of information technology made impact on managerial functions of the organization in the areas of recruitment, compensation, promotion, health benefit etc...
- ✓ All the respondents (100%) strongly agree that they could easily access and distribute information required due to the advancement of information technology.
- ✓ The majority (66%) of the respondents strongly agree that the application of biometric help the management by providing accurate information regarding employees' leaves and absenteeism.
- ✓ The majority (70%) of the respondent strongly agree that the advancement of information technology has made impact on policy formulation.
- ✓ The majority (60%) of the respondents agree that the management has taken correct decisions because of accurate data available through related software and internet.
- ✓ The majority (60%) of the respondents agree that the management can easily take legal decision with help of information technology.

- ✓ Majority (76%) of the respondents aware about information technology benefited to human resource department to access information of employees working in other departments.
- ✓ Majority (50%) of the respondents agree that advancement of information technology helped to aware about latest trends in policy making, activities and employment practices. It shows that management is creating a good rapport and commutation with their employees by providing information through internet regarding latest policies, various activities and employment practices related to work of the organisation. It helped the employees to understand their duties and responsibilities easily and to perform their work with expectation of management.
- ✓ Majority (58%) of the respondents agree that management has taken correct actions and decisions about human resource management through accurate data and up- to- date information available from internet and related software. The above data indicates that majority of the respondents agree that the information technology helped the management to access various information of employees regarding their leave, compensation, promotion, service, discipline procedure etc. which enables them to make correct decisions relating to human resource matters.
- ✓ Majority (80%) of the respondents said that they need latest technologies which help them to perform their wok more easily i.e. software related to induction programme, training, refresher courses with the help of information technology.

7. Suggestions:

Based on the findings of the study I would like make some suggestions:

- ✓ There should be a software which provide training and induction programmes to employees. It helped the trainer to reduce his work burden.
- ✓ Management should provide information to the employees regarding the benefits of information technology on work
- ✓ Management should employ more technical persons to handle the problems and work related to information technology.

8. Conclusion:

The advancement of information technology made various impacts on business organisation and its application on human resource management are many. The advent of information technology plays an important role in Human resource management by providing various information to the management regarding employees salary, experience, service, compensation etc...Therefore both management and employee are benefited with advent of information technology. The development of information technology and its impact on human resource management will be increased in future days.

References:

1. www.google.com

Topic: Impact of Information technology advancement on Human Resource Management: A study with special referen to Yenapoya University, Mangalore.

Questionnaire

A. Personal Details

1. Name :
2. Age : a. 20 – 25 yrs. () b. 30- 35 yrs. ()
c. 35- 40 yrs. () d. above 40 yrs. ()
3. Sex : a. Male () b. Female ()

4. Marital Status : a. Single () b. Married ()
5. Educational Qualification : a. SSLC () b. PUC ()
c. Graduate () f. Post Graduate () g. Other ()

B. Impact of information technology on Human Resource Management

1. How satisfied with the benefits of Information technology on Human Resource management.
a. Very Satisfied () b. Somewhat Satisfied ()
c. Neither Satisfied nor Dissatisfied ()
d. Somewhat Dissatisfied ()
e. Very Dissatisfied ()
2. Have you agree with the statement that “Advancement of Information Technology has reduced the work burden of employees in the organisation”
a. Strongly disagree () b. Disagree ()
c. Unsure () d. Agree () e. Strongly Agree ()
3. Do you agree that the employees’ work efficiency would have increased after that advancement of Information technology which makes the management work simple and easy.
a. Strongly disagree () b. Disagree ()
c. Unsure () d. Agree () e. Strongly Agree ()
4. Which of the following ways information technology made impact on Human Resource Management?

Particular	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Unsure	Agree	Strongly Agree
Managerial Functions					
Biometric					
Assess and distribute information					
Data storage and retrieval					
Policy formulation					
To make corrective actions					
Legal decision					

5. Do you agree that information technology has enabled HR department to connect through internet to the other departmental professionals to assess various information needed to manage employees.
a. Strongly disagree () b. Disagree ()
c. Unsure () d. Agree () e. Strongly Agree ()
6. Do you agree that IT advancement helped to create awareness of latest trends in policy making, activities and employment practices?
a. Strongly disagree () b. Disagree ()
c. Unsure () d. Agree () e. Strongly Agree ()
7. Do you believe that information technology has enabled the Management to take correct decisions and actions by providing accurate data and up- to- date information regarding various aspects of human resource in the organisation?
a. Strongly disagree () b. Disagree ()
c. Unsure () d. Agree () e. Strongly Agree ()
8. Do you have any suggestions to improve the role of Information technology in HRM?